

**SPECIAL DIDACTIC METHODS AND CORRECTIVE EXERCISES
USED IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BLIND CHILDREN**

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Summary: The most commonly used types are linear and needle. If we look at the history of pedagogy, several attempts have been made to create a relief dot font. In 1829, Louis Braille, a French pedagogue, created a relief dot font. This font has been used as a means of reading and writing for the blind all over the world.

In 1819, he was admitted to the institute for blind children in Paris. In this institute, pupils were given lessons in literacy, music, knitting and sewing. Textbooks written in raised-line font for classes were not available for many subjects. Students learned musical notes by listening and memorizing them.

Key words: visually impaired, organization, disabled, sight, honor, academician, abbreviated, didaskals, meningitis, brain tumor, meningoencephalitis

The development of the state and society, its prospects are determined by the intellectual level of the citizens living in this state. The degree of justice of the state is determined by its attention and care for the disabled. After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on November 18, 1991, the Law on Social Protection of the Disabled was adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Decisions No. 433, No. 520 of the State Program "Rehabilitation of Disabled Persons in the Republic of Uzbekistan" for 1996-2000, adopted on November 11, 1995, are proof of our opinion. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Social Protection of the Disabled", the State programs "Healthy Generation", "Mother and Child" of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan pay special attention to the issues of education, training, and social protection of disabled children.

The state cares for visually impaired children. In the education and upbringing of children in KNB, special correctional trainings are conducted together with general education knowledge. What is corrective training? We need to find an answer to this question.

In the preparation of blind and visually impaired children for work and independent life, special training aimed at improving their education and upbringing is important.

Correctional training includes: remedial physical training, rhythmic, correction of speech deficiency, work on development of vision. Children's general development features are taken into account in corrective training. Correctional training is carried out in close connection with education, which creates favorable conditions for the general development of children.

Remedial training is conducted in cooperation with the curriculum and program.

Rhythmic

Rhythmics is a system of physical exercises based on the cooperation of movement and music and is the main part of the physical education of anomalous children. Actions are performed in whole or in part on the basis of rhythm. Rhythmic development is a necessary condition for motor activity. A person who has a good sense of movement understands and assimilates the rhythmic nature of human movements.

Rhythmic training increases the body's ability to work, improves health, corrects physical development defects and movement disorders, controls the pace of movement. They inspire confidence in their actions.

In rhythmic classes, children get to know music, dance, and sing and master various movements. Rhythmic training includes: hand movements: running general development exercises (with and without objects) performed under the guidance of a teacher, dance, musical-rhythmic and movement games.

The prescribed program for rhythm includes 8 sections.

Theoretical information. Theoretical information is selected in such a way that the internal laws and complexity of the studied theoretical material are observed in the education of all ages. This ensures a successful learning process and keeps children interested in music.

Special rhythmic exercises. This is a simple type of methodological methods. This includes hand movement exercises, clapping exercises, and memorizing proverbs and poems. Such exercises develop not only the sense of speed, but also the breath. Special exercises are determined by the level of complexity.

Exercises in movement and music. Every exercise in this section relies on music. In the process of improvement of various movements, the teacher educates children in technical skills for performing exercises. Among them, the most important ones are: starting the movement when the music starts, adding the desired expression to the movement, and stopping the movement when the music ends.

Therapeutic physical education

It is a physical training tool used in the practice and treatment of various diseases.

Requires the implementation of a secondary task, which includes the physical development and movement readiness of children with visual impairments.

Disruption of the locomotor apparatus, violation of the functional composition of the body's physical system is specified separately. Disorders of the locomotor apparatus (scoliosis, flat feet and other diseases, disorders of the functional structure of the body's physical system include disorders of the muscular nervous system, respiratory system, cardiovascular system, vascular system, eye muscle system. The use of LFK in various eye diseases gives effective results, especially in glaucoma and myopia. It should be mentioned that the benefit of LFK is less effective in congenital nearsightedness (myopia).

The main tasks of therapeutic physical education are as follows:

- Strengthening the general organism;

- Improvement of functions in respiratory and cardiovascular systems;
- Improvement of blood circulation in eye tissues;
- Increase the working capacity of the eye muscle system;
- Strengthening the eye sclera.

The correct selection of the training complex brings success in correctional work with visually impaired children.

LFK training consists of preparation and basic starting stages.

To the task of the preparatory stage

- strengthening of the general organism;
- adaptation to physical load, i.e. adaptation;
- activation of respiratory and cardiovascular system;
- strengthening of the spine;
- including increasing emotional uplift.

During this period, it is necessary to perform special general development exercises for the head and trunk. A lot of attention is paid to correct breathing and correct exhalation. In addition, special exercises are performed to strengthen the heel. The above-mentioned exercises can be performed together with gymnastic objects (special sticks and balls). In the preparatory period, it is recommended to play not only gymnastic exercises, but also various action games. These games help to raise the mood of children and improve the overall health of the body.

Main period. The main tasks of this period are as follows:

- a) improvement of the blood circulation system in eye tissues
- b) strengthening the muscular system of the eye
- c) strengthening the sclera;

In addition to general development and breathing exercises performed at the initial stage, special eye exercises are performed. Special eye exercises are aimed at strengthening the external eye muscle and accommodation muscle. These exercises are carried out in harmony with general development exercises. The initial position is performed lying down and gymnastics leaning against the wall. It

is also advisable to massage the eyeball. 3 fingers are lightly pressed on the upper eyelid with the eyes closed. Eye opening and closing and blinking exercises are performed. It can last from 10 seconds to 1 minute.

Development of vision.

The use of psychophysiological and psychological-pedagogical methods is effective in the organization of visual development training. These methods are important in the development of all activities and sensory apparatus of visually impaired children, the main aspects and aspects of the subject are studied through psychophysiological methods.

For example: object shape size color.

Psychological pedagogical methods;

- subject;
- descriptive;
- computerized;
- television;
- includes project methods.

Object-oriented methods focus on the development of children's object-oriented practice of visual activity during exercises and games. Subject-based practical training includes modeling, construction, and various subjects.

Children learn to perceive objects by analyzing their shape, size, and color. Various images are used to develop vision. For example: black and white, color, outline, line drawing. In this place, the polychromatic tables created by Vitaly Pavlovich Yermakov, a doctor of pedagogic sciences, designed for the development, training and checking of vision are being used. These tests and tables are used in Russia, Japan, and China.

Boarding schools for blind and visually impaired children have the task of developing and protecting the sight of students, along with the tasks of general education and upbringing. These works are carried out at the school under the

guidance of an ophthalmologist, and medical nurses are actively involved in this process. Teachers and educators also contribute.

They monitor the timely execution of treatment procedures and strict adherence to the doctor's recommendations. Prescribing glasses and other optical vision correction devices is one of the main aspects of treatment.

Educators and caregivers should monitor children's proper use of glasses as recommended by the doctor. Choosing the right Ottrava is important. It should fit the size of the face and the distance between the pupils. Ottrava should not be allowed to heat the nose and ears.

Children often lose or break glasses. Therefore, it is necessary to order several glasses at once. Children should learn to keep their glasses clean and tidy. Some visually impaired students are prescribed telescopic glasses. They envision a binocular pedagogical-optical system. Contact lenses are recommended for near vision with pronounced astigmatism. Contact lenses are made of transparent plastic materials and hydrophilic plastic. They are worn directly under the eyelids to the eyelid. This type of correction is the most perfect. Plansphere, spherocylindrical, orthoscopy magnifiers are widely used in schools for visually impaired children. These magnifiers are made of organic glass. These magnifiers are a combination of two lenses.

Visually impaired children prefer to use magnifiers with 3.5-5 times magnification in their activities. Small ones cannot enlarge texts as much as they want. And large ones narrow the field of vision very much. Magnifiers are recommended by an ophthalmologist. Educators and educators should monitor their proper use and preservation. Magnifiers should be kept in separate boxes or bags. Children with optic nerve atrophy, ischopia, retinal dystrophy and other diseases need constant medical treatment during the course of the disease.

Elimination of speech defects.

As a result of logopedic assistance to visually impaired children: sensory deficiency is filled, cognitive activity of children is activated, personality qualities

are formed. Speech disorders are more common in blind and visually impaired children than in healthy children.

The importance of speech therapy in the education of blind and visually impaired children;

- correcting students' speech, reporting individual characteristics of speech defects;

- organization of work on sound culture of speech; logopedic ways of putting certain sounds; the sequence of work in the automation of sounds; creating manuals for logopedic work; speech therapists working in schools for blind and visually impaired children solve such tasks as the importance of conversation and games in strengthening speech skills. It is no secret that blind and visually impaired children have more speech defects than healthy children. As a result, blind and partially sighted children are not prepared or have difficulties in learning literacy.

A speech therapist working in a school for visually impaired students conducts training with blind and visually impaired students individually and face-to-face. Depending on the speech defect, deficiencies in the speech phonemic and grammatical structure of the students are eliminated. Literacy is taught, reading, writing, and speech are developed. A relief font is a special volume font adapted for reading and writing by blind children. In France in the middle of the 18th century, in order to develop the reading and writing skills of blind children, the French pedagogue V. G. Ganei proposed the enlarged form of the relief font based on the Latin alphabet. At the beginning of the 19th century, a much simplified typeface of the relief type appears.

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